

Object Pose Detection Through Touch Sensing

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Abstract—In this paper, we introduce a novel algorithm designed for robust assembly using only touch sensing. Visual systems are often not applicable due to various challenges, such as the object being fully or partially obscured from the camera, inadequate lighting conditions, or the camera’s size preventing assembly in tight spaces. In our research, we assume the availability of a 3D map of the object, but the precise pose of the object remains unknown. Additionally, we assume the object is not flat. We developed an algorithm to efficiently address these challenges, which aims to match touch sensing results with the object’s shape. Additionally, we provided extensions which efficiently handle uncertainties in the object map and touch sensing. The efficiency of the proposed algorithm is demonstrated through illustrative simulated use case and real robot experiments.

I. INTRODUCTION

In contemporary robotics, various sensors are employed to enable the execution of complex tasks [1]. These sensors include 2D and 3D cameras, force sensors, tactile sensors, laser scanners, and similar devices. Among these, cameras have proven to be particularly effective and cost-efficient for applications such as bin picking, object assembly, and quality control. However, challenges arise when objects are not visible due to overlap, poor lighting conditions, or suboptimal camera positioning. In such cases, reliance must shift to alternative sensors, such as force and touch sensors, which do not provide information as rich or comprehensive as that from cameras. This paper addresses this issue and proposes an alternative assembly method that does not rely on cameras.

A typical assembly operation, such as inserting a peg into a hole, can be divided into two primary phases: positioning the peg near the opening and the actual insertion. This paper does not address the insertion phase, where force sensors are necessary and has already been well studied in robotics.

Instead, we will focus on the approximation phase, i.e. localization of the opening, using only force sensors or touch detection.

Several heuristic and statistical search methods are commonly employed for this purpose, including random search [2], spiral search [3], genetic search [4], ergodic search [5] and others. Random and spiral searches do not require prior knowledge of the environment. In contrast, ergodic search utilizes a probability distribution indicating where the assembly object is likely to be located in space, making it more effective than the other two methods.

Our research advances this approach by assuming the availability of a sufficiently accurate model of the environment, albeit with an unknown location. The objective is to obtain the missing location information through systematic exploration.

II. STATE OF THE ART

Robotic mapping involves autonomous robots localizing themselves within a map or floor plan using sensor inputs, a challenge closely aligned with the focus of our study. However, most algorithms employed in robot mapping and navigation depend on a continuous influx of rich sensor data. This data is typically provided by cameras, laser scanners, and GPS systems for outdoor navigation, among other sensors. These technologies not only facilitate localization but also enable the simultaneous construction of maps through techniques such as Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM). Common computational methods utilized in these contexts include Kalman filtering, particle filters, and deep neural networks [6]. The problem of localization of objects during assembly operations was addressed in [7], [8], where they used an approach based on pre-acquired contact maps and particle filters. This method facilitated the precise localization of objects using sparse data, a significant advancement in the field. The

computationally efficient method for the 6-DOF localization applying the iterative Bayesian Monte Carlo technique was proposed in [9]. Similar goals were pursued in [10], where the expectation maximization-based Gaussian mixtures model was employed in detecting the contact state of peg-in-hole task using wrench signals only. Another relevant approach using tactile sensing applied to visual (2D) maps was proposed in [11]. Recursive Bayesian filtering was employed to estimate the belief distributions over all possible locations in the visual image. More recently, Bauza et al. [12] proposed a method that uses deep neural networks (DNN) to process high resolution tactile array data.

Despite these advances, most of the aforementioned research, with the exception of the work by Chhatpar et al. [7], [8], does not address the challenge of assembly pose search using binary touch sensors that provide very sparse data. This remains a critical area for further investigation to develop robust algorithms capable of operating with minimal sensory input.

III. MAP REGISTRATION

We assume that we have a precise enough 3D map of an object where we perform an assembly operation. For simplicity, we assume that assembly takes place on single surface of the object. This surface is represented with a 2D map \mathcal{M} defined in the x - y plane, divided into regions \mathcal{S}_i . Here, i denotes regions with roughly the same height z .

We color code these regions based on the value of i . Although this step is not absolutely necessary, it facilitates the representation of individual regions, implementation, and monitoring of the progress of the algorithm. This 2D map is known, but the location of the map is unknown to the robot. During the assembly, the robot touches different regions of the map. By measuring its z coordinate, it knows which region(s) were hit. The goal is to estimate the exact position of the map and therefore exact position of each region in robot coordinates. An example of such a map with regions is shown in Fig. 1.

Now assume that during the assembly, the robot should hit the goal region \mathcal{S}_g , e.g. \mathcal{S}_5 from Fig. 1. Although the robot has the position of the center of this region in its own coordinate system,

Fig. 1: A map with regions \mathcal{S}_i . Note that, the regions might be disjoint (e.g. \mathcal{S}_3). Each region is color-coded according to its z coordinate.

various reasons may cause inaccuracies, resulting in the robot hitting a different region, e.g. \mathcal{S}_2 . We introduce two coordinate systems: vectors with the superscript $(\cdot)^r$ are expressed in the robot's coordinate system, while those with the superscript $(\cdot)^m$ are expressed in map coordinate system. The transformation between the robot and the map coordinates is a homogeneous transformation matrix \mathbf{T} . We assume to know only the rotation of the transformation \mathbf{R} and the scaling γ , which appears due to different units applied for the map and the robot coordinates. The robot can identify the region by reading its z coordinate and determining the corresponding i . We denote this location by the vector $\mathbf{p}_0^r \in \mathcal{R}^2$. The location of \mathbf{p}_0^r is unknown in the map coordinate system, while the locations of the regions \mathcal{S}_i are unknown in the robot coordinate system. Our algorithm aims to estimate the location $\mathbf{p}_{0,e}^m \in \mathcal{R}^2$, which corresponds to the \mathbf{p}_0^r . Once the location of $\mathbf{p}_{0,e}^m$ is known with sufficient precision, we calculate the vector $\mathbf{d}^m = \mathbf{p}_c^m - \mathbf{p}_{0,e}^m$, where $\mathbf{p}_c^m \in \mathcal{R}^2$ is the goal location in the map coordinate system, e.g. the midpoint of the region \mathcal{S}_5 . In the next iteration, the robot hits the location calculated as $\mathbf{p}_0^r + \mathbf{d}^r$, where the mapping of the distance vector to the robot coordinates system is calculated as $\mathbf{d}^r = \gamma \mathbf{R} \mathbf{d}^m$.

First, we mark the region where the location \mathbf{p}_0^r lies as \mathcal{S}_s . We know this region because we know the coordinates z at the point where the

robot touched the point p_0^r . Then we estimate the point $p_{0,e}^m$. It is usually chosen in the midpoint of the region where the starting point is located, making sure that $p_{0,e}^m$ is contained in this region. If this is not the case, we select a random point that belongs to the region \mathcal{S}_s . Then we calculate the vector \mathbf{d}^m and pass it to the robot, which touches the surface at the point $\mathbf{p}_t^r = \mathbf{p}_0^r + \gamma \mathbf{R} \mathbf{d}^m$. From the z_t^r coordinate at the point, one can detect which region was touched. We denote this region by \mathcal{S}_t . The scalar γ is a scaling factor between distances in the robot coordinate system and the map coordinate system. The algorithm then selects all the points in the region \mathcal{S}_s that satisfy the condition that the vector $\mathbf{p}_{0,e}^m + \mathbf{d}$ is in the region \mathcal{S}_t . The selected points form a new selection set \mathcal{S}'_s with property $\mathcal{S}'_s \subset \mathcal{S}_s$. This assures that $\mathbf{p}_{0,e}^m$ converges towards \mathbf{p}_0^m . Note again that \mathbf{p}_0^m was not initially known. The entire procedure is summarized in Algorithm 1. In this algorithm, we applied the following functions:

- *TouchFloor* returns final z^r coordinate of the motion where the robot approaches the point \mathbf{p}_t^r with a z^r coordinate above the object and then moves in $-z$ direction until it touches the floor.
- *GetRegion* returns the region based on z^m coordinate.
- *GetCentroid* returns the center of the weight of the region.
- *RegisterRegions* returns the region composed of all points from the region \mathcal{S}_s that satisfy the condition that the vector $\mathbf{p}_{0,e}^m + \mathbf{d}^m$ is in the region $\mathcal{S}_t = \text{GetRegion}(z_t^m)$.

As already stated, the convergence of the algorithm is guaranteed if the search space is monotonically decreasing, $\mathcal{S}'_s \subset \mathcal{S}_s$. It is evident from the algorithm that the registration reduces the search area by at least by $\mathcal{S}'_s = \mathcal{S}_s - \mathbf{d}^m \mathcal{S}_g$. When $\mathcal{S}_s \subset \mathbf{d}^m \mathcal{S}_g$, then the position \mathbf{p}_t^r is within the goal region. This guarantees the effectiveness of the algorithm in systematically narrowing down the search area, ensuring convergence towards the target.

Let us illustrate the proposed map registration algorithm on the process of inserting the audio pin into the socket shown in Fig. 2. There are only three possible outcomes when inserting a pin

Algorithm 1: Map registration algorithm using touch sensing

Input: Map of the surface \mathcal{M} , Goal point \mathbf{p}_c^m , scaling factor γ between the robot units and map units

Output: Estimate of \mathbf{p}_0^m , robot at the goal point \mathbf{p}_c^m

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1  $\mathbf{p}_t^r = \mathbf{p}_0^r$ 
2  $z_t^r = \text{TouchFloor}(\mathbf{p}_t^r)$ 
3  $z_t^m = \mathbf{R}^T z_t^r / \gamma$ 
4  $\mathcal{S}_s = \text{GetRegion}(z_t^m)$ 
5 while  $z_t^m \neq z_c^m$  do
6    $\mathbf{p}_{0,e}^m = \text{GetCentroid}(\mathcal{S}_s)$ 
7   if  $\mathbf{p}_{0,e}^m \notin \mathcal{S}_s$  then
8      $\mathbf{p}_{0,e}^m = \text{rand}(\mathcal{S}_s)$ 
9    $\mathbf{d}^m = \mathbf{p}_c^m - \mathbf{p}_{0,e}^m$ 
10   $\mathbf{p}_t^r = \mathbf{p}_0^r + \mathbf{R} \gamma \mathbf{d}^m$ 
11   $z_t^r = \text{TouchFloor}(\mathbf{p}_t^r)$ 
12   $z_t^m = \mathbf{R}^T z_t^r / \gamma$ 
13   $\mathcal{S}_s = \text{RegisterRegions}(\mathcal{S}_s, \mathbf{d}, z_t^m)$ 

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Fig. 2: Audio pin and socket considered in toy example.

into the socket: (1) the pin is successfully inserted into the socket, (2) the pin hits the enclosure of the socket and (3) the pin misses the socket completely. Suppose that we are inserting a pin into a socket in the z direction of the base coordinate system. Cases (1) and (2) can be determined by observing the the robot's z coordinate when it touches the environment, while case (3) is determined with an excessive z coordinate. On the map, these areas are marked with yellow, blue and white color. In this example we examine the case where the initial guess \mathbf{p}_0^m is in the blue area, i.e. the robot hits the enclosure of the insertion socket. We create the binary mask composed of all regions with the sensed z coordinate and set them to 1, as show in the right part of the Fig. 3, 1 Next, we make a first estimate of the \mathbf{p}_0^m (marked by the red square) and sample the distance as $\mathbf{d}^m = \mathbf{p}_c^m - \mathbf{p}_{0,e}^m$ (red vector). In the next try, we touch the object with robot coordinates $\mathbf{p}_t^r = \mathbf{p}_0^r + \mathbf{R} \gamma \mathbf{d}^m$. This point is marked by the black cross. Note that in reality we

Fig. 3: An example of the registration of inserting the audio pin into the socket. Registration phases are labeled from 1 to 5. In the left images, the yellow area represents the center of the socket, the blue is the body of the socket, and the white is the exterior. With \times we marked position where the robot hit with the plug in each phase. The search area \mathcal{S}_s is marked in white in the corresponding right image. The red vector indicates \mathbf{d}^m . Red square indicates $\mathbf{p}_{0,e}^m$.

do not know the location of this point, we only know the area where the robot touched the object by knowing the robot z coordinate and its discrete counterpart h . By this we register all areas where the initial point \mathbf{p}_s^m is within the mask and the $\mathbf{p}_s^m + \mathbf{d}$ is in the area that the robot hit (in our case considered in Fig. 3, 2 this area is white). Based on this registration, the search area is reduced as shown in right part of the Fig. 3, 2. In this new search area we make new estimate of $\mathbf{p}_{0,e}^m$ and proceed as in the previous step. The search area \mathcal{S}_s is monotonically decreasing. When this area is smaller than the target area \mathcal{S}_g , the robot hits the goal, although in most cases this happens even before.

In an idealized and error-free simulated assembly, deterministic matching using a map can achieve uncertainty resolution to any desired level of accuracy. However, in practical robotic assembly, measurement and actuation errors pose significant challenges that make deterministic approaches less efficient and reliable. We can address this challenge by inflating¹ the search region \mathcal{S}_s . However, one has to set inflation rate carefully, as this can lead to instability of the search algorithm.

¹For example, using the "dilate" command in Open CV.

IV. SIMULATION AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In this section, we experimentally validate the performance of the proposed algorithm and compare it with a random search strategy. For all experiments, we used a 7DOF Franka Research 3 robot equipped with a modified impedance control law. The applied control law is detailed in [13], [14]. Enhancements to the original control law include bidirectional friction compensation, which improved positional accuracy for small displacements at low stiffness. The search motion was implemented by setting the velocity command in the direction of the surface normal and monitoring the force in the same direction. Motion was halted whenever the force exceeded a predefined threshold, and impact forces were mitigated by setting low stiffness in the direction of the surface normal.

Initially, we replicated the experiment described in the previous section. Here, the socket was placed on a table with its normal oriented in the z -direction, as depicted in Fig. 4. The socket was installed within a housing with a diameter of 2 cm, and the socket hole was 3.5 mm. The search area was confined to a square with a side length of 4 cm. The starting point was randomly selected within this area, ensuring that the socket opening was not encountered on the first attempt. For the robot to successfully position the plug in the socket, the endpoint deviation had to be within 0.3 mm. The search algorithm was limited to 12 trials. In 100 attempts, the algorithm successfully located the socket opening in two to ten attempts. Fig. 5 illustrates the convergence and standard deviation of the search process.

We conducted a comparative series of experiments using a random search within a 4 x 4 cm grid with a 0.2 mm resolution, ensuring no points were tested more than once. Fig. 6 shows the convergence and standard deviation of the random search. The results clearly demonstrate the superiority of the proposed search algorithm over random search, showing more than six times faster convergence on average and significantly lower variance, with more than twenty times faster convergence in the worst-case scenario.

The subsequent experiment pertains to the *Task Board*, an internet-connected device designed to

Fig. 4: Setup for testing of insertion of the audio pin into the socket.

Fig. 5: The convergence of the proposed search algorithm. The x axis shows the number of attempts and the left y axis shows the probability to hit the target. The right y axis shows the mean (5.83) and the standard deviation (2.04)

assess real-world robot manipulation skills [15]. Following the trial protocol established in 2023, one of the operations involves extracting a probe from its socket, measuring the probe’s voltage level, wrapping the cable, and then stowing the probe. The last operation often fails due to factors such as incomplete grasp of the probe, significant movements during manipulation, environmental contact with the probe, and the effects of pulling the probe cable. As part of the euRobin project², numerous Task Board manipulation solutions employing both in-hand and overhead cameras were introduced. However, these camera placements are inadequate for monitoring the probe-stowing operation. Consequently, an alternative solution utilizing touch detection was implemented for this purpose.

Initially, a 400 x 400 pixel map with depth information of the socket housing was provided, as depicted in Fig. 7. In this case, the insertion is along the robot’s x -axis. Each pixel represented 0.1 mm in robot coordinates, with the socket hole having a diameter of 4 mm. Following the protocol

²<https://www.eurobin-project.eu/>

Fig. 6: The convergence of the enhanced random search. The x axis shows the number of attempts and the left y axis shows the probability to hit the target. The right y axis shows the mean (37.37) and the standard deviation (36.55)

of previous experiments, 100 attempts were made to insert the probe into the socket, introducing random displacements of the starting point within the search area. In all attempts, the robot successfully inserted the probe into the socket within two to six tries. The convergence and standard deviation of the search algorithm for this scenario are shown in Fig. 8.

As demonstrated, the algorithm identified the target more quickly than in the previous example. This increased efficiency is attributed to the more complex environment, which provides additional information about the location during exploration.

Fig. 7: Setup for testing stowing the probe in the Task Board. The sub-figures on the left show a detail of the socket and a cross-section of the socket.

Both experimental use cases are additionally described in the attached videos, where the exploration of the algorithm and the process of evaluating the starting point can be observed.

V. CONCLUSION

In this study, we present a novel algorithm designed to locate an opening in a peg-in-hole

Fig. 8: The convergence of the proposed search algorithm. The x axis shows the number of attempts and the left y axis shows the probability to hit the target. The right y axis shows the mean (4.07) and the standard deviation (1.18)

assembly operation, utilizing solely touch information, supplemented by depth imaging of the object. The results demonstrate a remarkably fast convergence of the algorithm, with performance continuing to improve further in more complex environments. This initially counterintuitive outcome can be attributed to the fact that a more intricate environment provides the search algorithm with more informative cues, thereby accelerating convergence to the target location.

While our experiments focused exclusively on the localization of the target without considering its orientation, the proposed algorithm can be easily adapted to take into account orientation as well. This adaptation involves transforming planar search spaces into spatial or hyperspaces by incorporating additional orientation dimensions. Addressing these aspects will be a key focus of our future research endeavors.

In summary, the ability of our algorithm to effectively utilize environmental complexity to enhance search efficiency highlights its potential for broader applications in robotic assembly tasks. Future work will extend the algorithm's capabilities to include orientational search, thereby broadening its applicability and improving its robustness in diverse assembly scenarios.

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REFERENCES

- [1] S. E. Navarro, S. Mühlbacher-Karrer, H. Alagi, H. Zangl, K. Koyama, B. Hein, C. Duriez, and J. R. Smith, "Proximity perception in human-centered robotics: A survey on sensing systems and applications," *IEEE Transactions on Robotics*, vol. 38, no. 3, pp. 1599–1620, 2022.
- [2] F. Abu-Dakka, B. Nemeč, A. Kramberger, A. Buch, N. Krüger, and A. Ude, "Solving peg-in-hole tasks by human demonstration and exception strategies," *Industrial Robot*, vol. 41, no. 6, pp. 575–584, 2014.
- [3] F. Chen, F. Cannella, H. Sasaki, C. Canali, and T. Fukuda, "Error recovery strategies for electronic connectors mating in robotic fault-tolerant assembly system," in *2014 IEEE/ASME 10th International Conference on Mechatronic and Embedded Systems and Applications (MESA)*, 2014, pp. 1–6.
- [4] J. A. Marvel and W. S. Newman, "Assessing internal models for faster learning of robotic assembly," in *2010 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation*, 2010, pp. 2143–2148.
- [5] S. Shetty, J. Silvério, and S. Calinon, "Ergodic exploration using tensor train: Applications in insertion tasks," *IEEE Transactions on Robotics*, vol. 38, no. 2, pp. 906–921, 2022.
- [6] P. K. Panigrahi and S. K. Bisoy, "Localization strategies for autonomous mobile robots: A review," *Journal of King Saud University-Computer and Information Sciences*, vol. 34, no. 8, pp. 6019–6039, 2022.
- [7] S. Chhatpar and M. Branicky, "Localization for robotic assemblies with position uncertainty," in *Proceedings 2003 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS 2003) (Cat. No.03CH37453)*, vol. 3, 2003, pp. 2534–2540 vol.3.
- [8] —, "Particle filtering for localization in robotic assemblies with position uncertainty," in *2005 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems*, 2005, pp. 3610–3617.
- [9] A. Petrovskaya and O. Khatib, "Global localization of objects via touch," *IEEE Transactions on Robotics*, vol. 27, no. 3, pp. 569–585, 2011.
- [10] I. F. Jasim, P. W. Plapper, and H. Voos, "Position identification in force-guided robotic peg-in-hole assembly tasks," *Procedia CIRP*, vol. 23, pp. 217–222, 2014, 5th CATS 2014 - CIRP Conference on Assembly Technologies and Systems.
- [11] S. Luo, W. Mou, K. Althoefer, and H. Liu, "Localizing the object contact through matching tactile features with visual map," in *2015 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*. IEEE, May 2015.
- [12] M. Bauza, E. Valls, B. Lim, T. Sechopoulos, and A. Rodriguez, "Tactile object pose estimation from the first touch with geometric contact rendering," 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2012.05205>
- [13] B. Nemeč, M. M. Hrovat, M. Simonič, S. Shetty, S. Calinon, and A. Ude, "Robust execution of assembly policies using a pose invariant task representation," in *2023 20th International Conference on Ubiquitous Robots (UR)*, 2023, pp. 779–786.
- [14] M. Simonič, A. Ude, and B. Nemeč, "Hierarchical learning of robotic contact policies," *Robotics and Computer-Integrated Manufacturing*, vol. 86, 2024.
- [15] P. So, A. Sarabakha, F. Wu, U. Culha, F. J. Abu-Dakka, and S. Haddadin, "Digital robot judge: Building a task-centric performance database of real-world manipulation with electronic task boards," *IEEE Robotics & Automation Magazine*, pp. 2–14, 2023.